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Studies in Pyridothiazolopyrimidines and Pyridopyrimidothiazines

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SYNTHESIS of thiazoloquinazolines has been reported by the condensation of anthranilic acid with 2-Chloro thiazoles¹ and with allyl isothiocyanates². Attempts made for the synthesis of I on the same lines by the condensation of 2-amino nicotinic acid with 2-chlorothiazoles and allyl isothiocyanates were unsuccessful. The failure may be attributed to the less basic nature of amino group in 2-amino nicotinic acid. Synthesis of I has, however, been achieved by the condensation of 2-chloro nicotinic acid with 2-amino-4-aryl thiazoles. The chlorine here being hedged between two electron withdrawing groups should be more reactive. The yields of the products, however, remained very poor. It may be due to the lack of requisite basicity of amino group in 2-amino-4-arylthiazoles.

Similarly condensation of 2-chloro-4 : 6-dimethyl-5-nitro-nicotinitrile (III) have been carried out with 2-amino-4-aryl thiazoles IV to furnish I.

Condensation of III with 2-thio-4 : 4 : 6-trialkyl-1 : 4-dihydropyrimidine furnished 2 : 2 : 4-trialkyl-7 : 9-dimethyl-8-nitro-2H, 6H-pyrido (3,2-a) pyrimido (2,1-b) (1,3)thiazin-6-one (II).

Experimental

6 : 8-Dimethyl-7-nitro-3-phenyl-5H-pyrido(2,3-d) thiazolo(3,2-a) pyrimidin-5-one (Ia) :

A mixture of 2-amino-4-phenyl thiazole³ (1.76 g, 0.01 mole) and 2-chloro-4 : 6-dimethyl-5-nitro nicotinic acid⁴⁻⁶ (2.3 g, 0.01 mole) was heated at 140°-50° for half an hour and the temperature was gradually raised to 180°-90° where it was maintained for half an hour. The solid mass was treated with sodium carbonate solution (10%), filtered and the residue was washed with water and then treated with ethanol (10 ml) and filtered again. The ethanolic filtrate on dilution with water furnished a compound (1 g) which after crystallisation was found to be 2-amino-4-phenyl thiazole, m.p. 150°. The ethanol insoluble product on crystallisation from dioxan gave (Ia) 0.43 g. in 15% yield, m.p. 221°. Found : N, 15.64. C₁₇H₁₂N₄SO₃ requires, N, 15.90%. Ib m.p. 180°, yield 12%, Found : C, 58.78; H, 2.45; N, 14.28%. C₁₇H₁₁ClN₄SO₃ requires, C, 58.84; H, 2.84; N, 14.54%. I.R. 1620 (>C=N-), 1680 (amidic keto) and 1580 cm⁻¹ (due to a combination of C, N and S⁷). Ic, m.p. 208°, yield 14%, Found : N, 15.50; C₁₈H₁₄N₄SO₃ requires, N, 15.30%. Id m.p. 210°-11°, yield 40%. Found : N, 15.87; C₁₆H₁₈N₅SO₄ requires, N, 16.24%.

2 : 2 : 4 : 7 : 9-Penta methyl-8-nitro-2H,-6H-pyrido(3,2-e) pyrimido (2,1-b) (1,3) thiazin-6-one (IIa).

2-Chloro-4 : 6-dimethyl-5-nitro nicotinic acid (2.3 g, 0.01 mole) and 2-thio-4 : 4 : 6-trimethyl-1 : 4-dihydropyrimidine⁸ (1.56 g, 0.01 mole) were heated together in an oil bath at 160° for 3 hr. The resulting product (IIa) was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 240°. Found : N, 16.44; C₁₆H₁₆N₄SO₃ requires, N, 16.80%. IIb, m.p. 230°. Found : N, 15.57; C₁₆H₁₈N₄SO₃ requires, N, 15.55%.

Fig. I. (III, Y = COOH) Ia, X = O, R = H
 Ib, X = O, R = Cl
 Ic, X = O, R = CH₃
 Id, X = NH, R = OC₂H₅
 HCl
 (III, Y = CN),

Fig. II. IIa, R = CH₃
 IIb, R = C₂H₅

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Studies on Heteropoly Acids of Antimony (V) Molybdates

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THE present communication deals with the formation and stability of a heteropoly acid of antimony (V) with molybdates. Previous reports¹ on such studies are inadequate.

50 ml of *M*/20 molybdic acid solution was refluxed with 80 ml of *M*/75 potassium pyroantimonate solution for 45 min. and then evaporated to crystallisation to get fine needle shaped cream coloured crystals. The observed percentage of antimony and molybdenum in the compound came to 4.28% and 41.09% respectively against the theoretical calculated values 4.31% and 41.11%. The ratio between antimony and molybdenum was 1 : 12, which agreed with the formula $H_3[(Sb Mo_{12}O_{40})] \cdot 48 H_2O$. The final representation of the formula was according to the views of Keggin².

Determination of Basicity :

By titration of the compound in the borax solution its basicity was found to be 3. To know if all the hydrogen atoms are equally ionisable under the same condition, the above titration was also done conductometrically. The result indicated that out of the three hydrogen atoms one is held differently.

Determination of Isothermals :

To find out the number of water of constitution, use was made of the apparatus described by Ray and

Sinha³ and subsequently modified by Bhattacharya and Sinha⁴. Following the usual methods of step-wise dissociation at 30° and 40°, it was observed that the number of water of constitution was 8H₂O. This agreed with the work of Scroggie and Clark⁵ with comparable compounds.

Determination of Molecular weight by X-ray : Diffraction Method :

Cryoscopic method was applied to have an approximate idea about the molecular weight which came to 2572. It is necessary to have a very accurate data for the molecular weight to know definitely whether the molecule is dimeric or single. With the help of the analysis by X-ray photography diffraction pattern of the compound the volume per unit cell *V* was found to be 3967. The crystal being orthorhombic in shape ($\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$), the number of unit cell *n* was analysed to be 4. The observed density ρ was determined by displacement method and it came to 4.64. By applying these data to the expression, $\rho = \frac{1.66 M.n}{V}$, the molecular weight of

the compound came to 2772.2 which closely agreed with the theoretically calculated molecular weight of the compound as 2781.

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A note on potential difference between two reversible electrodes, one placed in the colloidal solution and the other in the intermicellar liquid

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THE existence of a potential difference between two reversible electrodes, one placed in the colloidal solution and the other in the intermicellar liquid (separated from the colloidal solution by dialysis, ultrafiltration etc.) the two being in direct contact, has been the subject of much controversy^{1,2,3}.